

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BHALEKAR****FIRST NAME: ASHVIN****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied **UK** conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author **did** use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author **did** use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: **MSWord**

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which style guide does EUCLID recommend?

- The Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association (APA).
- Chicago Rules (Turabian).**¹
- The Modern Language Association's (MLA) Handbook.
- Oxford Standard for Citation of Legal Authorities (OSCALA).

2. When can a *hyphen* be used in a sentence?

- In noun phrases.
- In an adjectival phrase following a noun.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 141.

- In an adjectival phrase before the noun.**²
- If a compound that would normally be hyphenated is preceded and modified by an adverb.
3. When should an in-text citation be used?
- When stating common knowledge.
- When expressing personal opinions.
- When using someone else's ideas or direct words.**³
- When summarizing general knowledge.
4. What is the purpose of a style guide in academic writing?
- To ensure consistency in formatting, citation, and structure.**⁴
- To make writing more creative.
- To eliminate the need for citations.
- To allow personal preferences in writing.
5. What is the last element of an argument called?
- Warrant.**⁵
- Claim.
- Reason.
- Response.

² Ibid., 21.

³ Ibid., 35.

⁴ Ibid., 40.

⁵ Kate Turabian *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 62.

6. Which of the following does not refer to the *author-date style*?
- Turabian style.
 - Oxford Standard for Citation of Legal Authorities (OSCALA).**⁶
 - Chicago author-date.
 - Reference list style.
7. Which type of sources are called primary sources?
- Original documents.**⁷
 - Books from a reputable university press.
 - Dictionaries and encyclopedias.
 - Online blogs and opinion articles.
8. What is a key strategy to avoid plagiarism?
- Using a source of information and giving credit to the publisher of the source of information.
 - Properly citing sources and using quotation marks where needed.**⁸
 - Paraphrasing without mentioning the original source.
 - Copying and pasting without changes.
9. Which of the following is not included in a dissertation concept paper?

⁶ Ibid., 228.

⁷ Ibid., 36.

⁸ Ibid., 370.

- Abstract.**⁹
- Statement of the Problem.
- Research Questions.
- Research Design.

10. Which of the following statements about full stops is CORRECT?

- A full stop must always be placed at the end of a heading.
- Footnotes always end with a full stop, regardless of content.
- If a sentence ends with an ellipsis (...), no additional full stop is required.**¹⁰
- A full stop should be placed at the end of every quotation, even if it already ends with a punctuation mark.

⁹ James P Sampson *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

¹⁰ European Commission *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in European Commission* 8th ed. (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2021), 7.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.